

What are the usage dimensions of open?

OSI 2016: Final Presentation

The team

Identified Areas of Priority

Character of Outputs &
Research workflow

Flexible economics

Stakeholders

- Researchers & Librarians
- Funders
- Service Providers
- Public

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Areas needing solutions

Standards and norms

Exit strategies

Incentive systems

Inertia balanced with the desire for change while maintaining continuity

A working group of major funders to:

Facilitate budgeting to support OA.

Use workflow tools e.g. ORCID

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* Someone (Force11?) take up the creation of 1-pager that speaks to these issues to funders?

Intelligent partnerships

To make things easier for researchers

Landscape assessment for current best practices, standards, norms

Exit strategies

a means of leaving one's current situation with a path to sustainability through considering appropriate governance

Propose an idea workshop in the area of exit strategies/ sustainability to develop project solicitations

Industry involvement in #OSI2017: Google, Microsoft, Amazon

Use available resources: JISC, JSTor, Ithaka

Educating sustainers

Inclusion of
#OpenResearch in
disciplinary curricula

Funder teaching/training
grants (e.g., NIH BEST)

Get AAU & APLU & AAMC
in on the game of open
scholarship: Thoughts,
concerns, opportunities for
change.

nSCI, **keep up**
the good
work!

References

- 101 Innovations in Scholarly Communications: <https://innoscholcomm.silk.co/>
- Association of American Universities: <http://www.aau.edu/>
- Association of Public & Land-Grant Universities: <http://www.aplu.org/>
- Association of American Medical Colleges: <https://www.aamc.org/>
- Broadening Experiences in Scientific Training: <http://www.nihbest.org/>
- Jisc: <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/>
- JSTOR: <http://www.jstor.org/>
- ITHAKA: <http://www.ithaka.org/>
- nSCI: <http://nationalscience.org/>

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 Follow

The most contentious debate in our workgroup was whether this should live or die [#OSI2016](#)

References

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